

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THE INFLUENCE OF THE USE OF PISA TASKS ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE PROCESS OF TEACHING PHYSICS IN ENGLISH

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Abstract

Today, in the context of a conceptual education system: digitalization of the educational process, digital educational content, digitalization of education management, the formation of subject and communicative language competencies of a future physics teacher as a result of mastering subjects in English is of great importance professionally. Therefore, an urgent problem is the use of advanced technologies for teaching natural sciences, including physics in English. Considering that the international PISA program is aimed at assessing the ability to apply knowledge in various life situations, the ability to solve problems not directly related to specific academic disciplines, it is known that the use of PISA tasks in the development of new materials is of interest to students. This article discusses the significance and features of PISA assignments in the development of the process of teaching physics in English. The research analyzed scientific papers related to the use of digital educational, STEAM educational technologies in teaching physics in English. In addition, a review of works related to the use of PISA assignments in teaching physics was conducted. Work has been carried out to develop tools to improve the effectiveness of teaching physics in English. In addition, questionnaires and control work of students in physics were organized. The study showed that the use of 3D - basic computer programs necessary to create STEAM resources, combined with PISA tasks, increases the efficiency of the educational process. The results of the study are recommended for use in the process of teaching physics and the development of educational and methodological complexes for teaching physics in English.

Keywords: future physics teachers, English, PISA assignments, digital educational resources, educational process.

Introduction

Currently, the Kazakhstan education system is faced with the problem of increasing the competitiveness of the quality of education and adaptation to real life stages, since a person lives and works in conditions that require high professionalism and intellectual activity to make the right decisions in society associated with various life problems.

Our preliminary research shows the crisis in the technical and engineering workforce in our country. According to employers and industries, this problem is caused by low academic performance in physical and mathematical disciplines in education, low motivation for teaching steam disciplines and the fact that technical and engineering specialties are chosen less often than others. At the same time, a large demand (STEM employees) for specialists with a new type of engineering thinking and inventive potential, a set of competencies for the development and management of technologies, qualified specialists with knowledge of the English language with practical skills in working with complex technological objects was revealed.

These requests set the task not only to improve existing knowledge, but also to find new ways to prepare future specialists for solving specific problems of the

world around them. This task showed the relevance of our research topic.

At each stage of the study of the International Student Assessment Program PISA (program for International Student Assessment), differentiation is carried out in an international context. Thus, each participating country will be able to determine its strategic goals for the education system [1].

The PISA test is fundamentally different from the usual exams and tests of students. In the course of this large-scale study, it is not the level of mastery of the school curriculum that is assessed, but the ability of young students to apply their knowledge in life situations. Types of open and closed tasks are included in the test. Some tasks consist of several questions of different levels depending on the living conditions.

Therefore, we reviewed the works related to the use of PISA tasks in teaching physics. In the works of Hijriati Sahyar and Derlina, the problem of creating a test tool in physics based on PISA for an optical subject in a high school with a valid category is considered. At the stage of Needs Analysis and analysis of literature research materials, it was found that the differences in assessment are small, and it is difficult for students to

find references to Pisa-based physics questions, especially optical materials. The material for the developed physical problems includes optical phenomena, light reflection, light refraction and optical instruments [2].

W.Sahyar, Bunawan, J.Yanti studies analyze the three competencies of Pisa Scientific Literacy, which are determined by each knowledge on the main topics of Physics [3].

In addition, in the research of our domestic scientists Yerbol Sarmurzin, Nazerke Amanzhol, Kamshat Toleubayeva, Marina Zhunusova, Aray Amanova, it is noted that reforms and updates in the field of education are constantly taking place. The authors note that despite the impact of the International Student Assessment Program (PISA) as a global phenomenon, how Kazakhstan has adopted this international test, and the fact that PISA has practically not affected the results of students, it is still taken into account for achievements in the field of Education [4].

Scientific research work on the importance of the PISA program in teaching physics shows that it is aimed at evaluating learning outcomes. However, according to the PISA program, it was found that there is not enough research on the formation of certain competencies for tasks. That is why we set out to study the impact of the use of PISA tasks on the development of subject-language competence of students.

Close to the topic of our research, the problem of developing subject-language competence of students did not go unnoticed by researchers. Fernando, A.[5]. at the Faculty of natural sciences, he organized training classes "Learn in English", studied the problems of integrated teaching of Natural Sciences in English. The scientist was experimentally convinced of the effectiveness of the design teaching method. Natalia S. Godzhaeva, Timur A. Logunov [6] presented to Russian universities the stages of the implementation of CLIL technology. In addition, A.Özbay, M. Kayaoğlu [7] studied the problems of teaching physics in English based on the REACT strategy.

K. Shaimerdenova from domestic scientists., A. Tussypbaeva[8] in the works of A. Kodussov, A. Beibitova [9], who studied the effectiveness of teaching Physics and astronomy in secondary schools using a workbook in English, there is information about effective ways, methods and methods of integrated teaching of subjects in a foreign language.

In the country, teaching English to school teachers in natural science subjects is carried out through advanced technologies from the National Center for advanced training "Orleu" and other organizational centers. However, at present, changes in the education system make it necessary to develop the language competence of future specialists in universities and train them competitively in their professional activities.

Having reviewed foreign and domestic literature, you can master effective technologies for the development of subject and communicative-language competencies. However, at a time when the topic of research is of high importance in the country, there is a lack of research in this direction.

There are many difficulties in the development of this direction, especially due to the lack of research in

the field of developing subject – language competence in the study of disciplines in the technical and Natural Sciences, in particular physics, the lack of accurate and systematic didactics of teaching, the lack of advanced technologies, teaching tools and effective methods.

A theoretical analysis of the above works suggests that although their study of the problems of using CLIL technologies in teaching students in higher education, the problem of training future physics specialists in English on the basis of the development of subject and communicative-language competence of students in the conditions under consideration is still scientifically unresolved. Contradictions arise between the need to use digital educational resources in order to develop the subject-language competence of students and the need for innovative technologies, methodological and computer software tools in its implementation and the lack of research on the system of training students on the basis of the development of their subject and communicative-language competence through the creation and use of digital resources.

Research methodology

In accordance with the goals and objectives of the study, the following methods were used in the study: analysis of articles published in high-ranking scientific journals in the Scopus, Web of science databases. The analysis was carried out on the basis of the keywords "PISA tasks", "Physics teaching", "application orientation", "CLIL", "digital technologies", etc. In addition, in the course of the study, the method of questionnaires, interviews was used. In order to effectively implement the teaching of physics in English in the training of students through PISA tasks, an analysis of several programs and standards was carried out. A total of 70 people from University students and schoolchildren took part in the survey.

An anonymous questionnaire for schoolchildren about PISA tasks can be viewed below.

1. Have you heard of the international PISA study?
 - Yes, of course I heard
 - No, not heard at all
2. What is the international PISA study? How do you understand?
3. Have you ever participated in the international PISA study?
 - Yes, I participated
 - No, did not participate
4. Have you completed PISA tasks in Physics?
 - Yes
 - No
5. how difficult will it be for you to complete the PISA tasks?
6. Can you complete PISA tasks on your own?
 - Yes
 - No
 - I find it difficult to answer
7. which direction do you think is the most difficult according to the international PISA study?
 - Reading literacy
 - Mathematical literacy
 - Natural science literacy

8. are you satisfied during the preparation for PISA? Why not?

9. Do you want to include an optional lesson in the school program "on the international study of PISA"?

- Yes
- No

10. do you think PISA tasks affect the development of your scientific mindset?

The main part

An analysis of articles published in high-ranking scientific journals in the Scopus, Web of science databases showed that the problems of using CLIL technology in the training of future physics teachers and teaching a school physics course are currently being studied by foreign and domestic scientists.

Finnish scientists L.Kääntä, G.Kasper, A.Piirainen-Marsh [10] considers the effectiveness of the Content-and-Language-Integrated-Learning (CLIL) program in the physics class taught in English. This lesson is devoted to the interpretation of "Hooke's law", defining its basic concepts and their relationship as instructive questions. Using tasks for the formation of language skills "pronunciation" (Figure 1), the article shows how the teacher performs actions related to definitions and definitions through "conversation". The results obtained contribute to understanding how to establish knowledge of physical laws as a professional work of a teacher in the case of CLIL.

<p>Water</p>		
<p>Wood</p>		
<p>Brick</p>		
<p>Gold</p>		

Figure 1 - task for the formation of language skills (www.tes.co.uk)

In Sweden, from the point of view of disciplinary discourse, it can be said that subject and language integrated learning (CLIL) has come into use in all university courses, even in monolingual environments. Obviously, the situation becomes more complicated when teaching in two or more languages is involved. In the article by Swedish scientists "I don't teach language": the linguistic attitudes of physics lecturers in Sweden", the main goal is to acquaint readers with the linguistic situation in Swedish universities, showing that two languages - English and Swedish — are widely used in teaching a number of disciplines [11].

A.Jameau, C.Le Hénaff [12] research is devoted to the didactic analysis(subscription, reading) of teaching non - linguistic subjects in English - Physics and chemistry-within the framework of CLIL programs. On the example of a science teacher, the relationship between scientific knowledge and language knowledge

is described. As a result of the study, scientists cited recommendations for training teachers who teach under CLIL programs.

H.Çelik, U.Sari, U.N.Harwanto [13] examines the language perception of physics teachers in computer learning practice (CBL) using a virtual physical program in their research. In this study, the Algodoo program (Figure 2) and the SMART board were used to implement the virtual environment. According to the curriculum in the field of physics in Turkey, 37 people studying the pedagogical skills of Kyrykkale University at the Faculty of Education took part. The case study method was used and the data was collected by researchers. The results of this study showed that the use of a simulation program in language integrated teaching of physics has a positive effect and can improve students' understanding.

Figure 2 - the existing Algodoo program to implement the virtual environment (<http://www.algodoo.com>)

Domestic scientists B. Zhetpisbaeva. A. Kitibaeva., D. Kazimova [14] in the research work considered the content of integrated learning and the assessment of language skills. In order to achieve the effectiveness of teaching subjects in English in a comprehensive school, a special organization of the educational process in the lessons showed the need to change the approach to planning and determining goals, evaluating learning outcomes, selecting educational materials, combining the content of subjects and the process of teaching the language. In order to study the practice of CLIL assessment, the authors conducted a study among teachers of the Karaganda region teaching biology, chemistry, physics and computer science in

English; a detailed analysis of the results of this study was presented. The main task of monitoring the development of language skills and their assessment was to create a system of language learning goals for CLIL.

In our study, we used PISA assignments during the lesson to observe the impact on mastering physics in English.

For example, the picture shows a plan of the treadmills of a small stadium. The center of the Square is a rectangular area with two semicircular shapes on the right and left sides. The width of each treadmills is equal to 1 meter.

Figure 3 - Marking of the athletics stadium (<https://ru.wikipedia.org/>)

With the first line on the inside, what is the distance when one lap is run. Show your way of solving. We used Pisa character tasks like this one on each topic.

In the course of scientific research, it school-Lyceum No. 23 named after zh.Tashenov was taken as the base, and a study was conducted for students of the 9th grade. Students of the 9th "B" grade were selected as the object of the study. During the research work, first of all, an anonymous survey of students about the international PISA study was obtained. The survey involved 26 students aged 14-15 years.

A survey is an effective tool for getting feedback from an audience, as well as seeing what that audience is like.

According to the results of the survey, it turned out that 70% of students were aware of the international PISA study, and 30% did not hear it at all. It turns out

that students in this class did not participate in the international PISA research. However, before that, a large number of students say that they have completed PISA tasks in physics, and it turned out that it is difficult for them to complete PISA tasks.

The PISA program assesses the literacy rate of students in three main areas. These are: reading literacy, mathematical and natural science literacy. According to students, 60% think that natural science literacy is complex, and the remaining 40% think that mathematical literacy is complex. Students want to introduce an optional lesson that they will prepare on the "PISA international study". PISA tasks have a direct impact on the development of scientific thinking of students.

Conclusion

Analyzing the best foreign and domestic scientific experience, we identified the main opportunities for effective implementation of integrated subject-language training in the training of students:

- to ensure that the teaching of basic disciplines of future physics specialists in higher education has an impact on the acquisition of English as an auxiliary tool;

- take into account interdisciplinary connections in the study of basic disciplines of the specialty physics and coordinate the material passed in terms of time;

- formation of interdisciplinary knowledge of scientific theories and laws in English by future physics specialists, combined with their generality, skills and abilities;

- the ability of future physics specialists to learn from another subject in the course of studying one subject, to widely use their skills and abilities;

- the ability to show the commonality and specificity of research methods of different disciplines in the training of future physics specialists;

- the use of PISA tasks, revealing the common relationship of phenomena studied in the subject lessons of future physics specialists.

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